

DEVELOPMENT OF TERRITORIAL SYSTEMS OF RECREATION INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE

Djuraeva Lobar Vohidovna

Teacher of the Chirchik State Pedagogical Institute of the Tashkent region

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6672989>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th May 2022

Accepted: 02nd June 2022

Online: 05th June 2022

KEY WORDS

recreation, countries, tourism, resort area, healing waters, spring, mud, climate, treatment.

ABSTRACT

This article presents the experience of foreign countries, including Turkey, the Czech Republic, Russia and Kyrgyzstan in the development of recreational systems.

According to the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), in recent years, tourism has become the fourth largest export of world goods and services and has become one of the leading industries in the current state and conditions of world economic development. The report of this organization states that "special attention should be paid to the issues of sustainable development of such types of tourism as ecotourism, recreational skitourism, extreme, pilgrimage, gastronomic tourism. These tasks are aimed at conducting research aimed at developing routes in areas with high population density and rich in various tourism resources.

Today Baptist pastor Thomas Cook, recognized as the founder of modern tourism, was one of the first mass travelers. He understood the essence and usefulness of his organization, and in 1843 he organized the type of the first railway and succeeded in achieving it. In

1851, Englishmen from all over the country joined him. He organized his participation in an exhibition in Paris. He had the honor of bringing 165,000 people to the exhibition. Exhibition types are a big advantage Cook brought British tourists to Paris in 1855. Mass visits to the World Expo became the organizer. Since 1856, tourism throughout Europe has become commonplace. became Cook's travel agency and its affiliates. Travel company achieves unprecedented success The catalog that Cook offers to tourists also confirms the presence of more than 8,000 hotels. In 1870, the number of clients of the travel company "Thomas Cook" reached 500 thousand people. Regular transportation between the European and American continents 1832 was founded in 1866 by Cook's tourists to the United States sends the first two groups. View long-lived, up to five months continuation An American celebrity who used the services of Thomas

Cook, one of the tourists was Mark Twain, a group of sixty people participated in the composition and later wrote this trip. Thomas Cook. In 1872, he was the first to circumnavigate the world on an industrial basis. He proposed to organize the first 20 travelers - these are 220 people around the world who traveled during the day. Thomas Cook died in 1892, his business was continued by his sons and partners. The company operated independently, expanded its scope and became a major financial institution and travelers began issuing traveler's checks.

This is, in fact, the invention of the century - there was safe money. Today Thomas Cook is all over the world. It has over 12,000 travel agencies and serves more tourists with over 20 million a year.

Traveling life is new as a particularly attractive way of doing business. Kind-tourism is different, it has its own characteristics and qualities that have been characterized. The main aspect that distinguishes tourism from travel is purpose and popularity. Prosper Merimee was recorded in 1840 in Colombes. "Instead of the constant joy of tourists, indifference appears, come, most of the tourists present, to stand out in their own way, choosing for themselves the motto *Neil Admirare* (nothing to be surprised)

It should be noted that these are the concepts of "traveler" and "tourist". was the first difference between.

The desire to stand out among other people, to be the first stands out among travelers. In addition to human activities, there are more opportunities to express yourself here than in the fields. Who goes up the most and drinks champagne, who is

further, who will be more at the stations or border crossings - the record is the imagination of travelers is limitless, the Guinness Book of Records The book has a separate section on such achievements.

In 1913, he traveled around the world, traveling 50,000 km. and 52 tires, 36 tubes, 9 chains, 9 pedals, 4 saddles, Replaced 2 rudders, etc. and the "Brilliant Star" sign (-1931) in which he rode his bicycle along the borders of the USSR. Gleb Travin can also be included in the list of travelers for several years during the Tatra cars on all continents of the planet. Czechoslovak travelers who organized the trip Jiri Ganzelka and Stanislav To enroll the Zigmuds in the category of tourists, of course, difficult. Their financial and technical in the intercontinental direction "Tatra", provided that it served the advertising purposes of the company. In practice, this is normal and for a fee for the testers of technical requirements for the provision of services.

Intends to surprise others in the Guinness Book of Records, a lot of space is devoted to organized travel and adventure. A man named Jesse Rosedale has traveled to most countries of the world and has his own target, which he covered the distance of 2,627,766 km and 215 crossed the border of the country and received a Guinness diploma for, stands Missionary Alfred Waldern (USA) on horseback. Horse target and distance 424,850 km (whether one or more is unknown) on horseback. At the same time, he gave more than 16,000 lectures. walking, skiing, cycling, road, rail, air and sea transport have also set various travel records. Even a scientist who travels in time and space, landing on the Moon, astronauts on

Earth, flying in their orbits (they can also be included in the list of tourists) also strive to set a record. In space, the first person to fly, the first female astronaut, the duration of the flight, altitude and distance, the duration of the lunar cruise on the lunar surface and a number of other facts will be the basis for recording in the protocol. This is when considering the differences between travel and tourism, it is necessary to dwell on the goals and material support of the activity. Travel and the bulk of expeditions in specific areas (trade, science, new reclamation, product advertising, etc.) are financed by individuals, organizations, public and private foundations.

Traveling is first and foremost a profession, people's profession or a source of daylight or the marriage of the participants of the journey can become a style. This is the purpose of activities, tourism is different from their goals. Time has significantly changed the possibilities of man. Today, almost everyone has free time and enough money to travel around the world in a balloon or other transport, they can visit places in the world that are untouched by the human foot. Travel companies specializing in adventure tourism.

Long-term (up to 30 weeks) intercontinental travel in custom-made vehicles across America, Africa and Asia. Large repetition of directions by new land surveyors, costing 50 thousand US dollars. 190-day, \$1 billion cruises are also offered. Known for the organization and implementation of tourism in the conditions of this tourism industry enterprises and tourism from tourism services provided by organizations can be used. Although it is a

type of tourism, but in itself has a specific description, according to which the person involved is a tourist.

Unlike travel, tourism is a strong economy and politics is an area of influence, in addition to the dualism of internal natural phenomenon will have Tourism is carried out by these tourists, a well-defined type of public transport with tourism purposes, i.e. activities and services for organizing and conducting such trips provider organizations. Such activities are distinguished by tourism performed by industrial enterprises and related industries increased.

Tourist activities are mainly carried out in free time. That's what happens for this there must be two conditions: free time and appropriate funds. For a long time tourism was only for the rich belonging to the stratum. Currently, various segments of the population are vacant time and savings on various tourist trips.

Tourism In the 21st century, tourism in its current sense was formed at the end of the 19th century, but only in the 20th century it became more dynamic, and the development of technology and technology, society as a result of the emergence of relations, he called it a "phenomenon of the twentieth century." Today, tourism is a very strong sector of the world economy, with a share of 10% of world GDP, and attracts a large number of workers, fixed assets and large capital investments. This is big business, big money and global is a serious policy on a scale.

In order to determine the specific features of modern tourism, it will be necessary to identify its important classification features.

Including, geographical indications, direction of tourist flow, destination, mode of transportation, means of

accommodation for tourists and classification of legal forms by the number of participants is appropriate.

Bans in this area are a priority in the world, especially in recent years to identify the tourism potential of the regions, develop and develop new tourist routes.

The country is undergoing a number of reforms aimed at developing the tourism industry, expanding tourism and related infrastructure in the regions, creating new tourism facilities and achieving significant positive results.

It is known that recreation is one of the main profitable sectors of the economy. Some countries with developed recreational activities have significantly improved their economies as a result of the uninterrupted flow of recreation. A number of measures are being taken in our country to develop this sector. In particular, the Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 362 of September 6, 2001 "On additional measures to preserve the natural resources of the Chimen-Charvak resort and recreation system and improve the system of recreation and health improvement" pays special attention to the development of recreation in the region.

It should be noted that the development and application of the experience of foreign countries in the innovative development of recreational complexes in our country will contribute to the further development of this area. In most developed countries, the process of establishing recreational activities began earlier than in developed countries, and they have accumulated rich experience in this area. One of the urgent tasks today is the

application of the experience of these countries in the further development of recreation in the country, their use in the organization of recreational services.

In particular, today Turkey has become one of the most visited countries in Europe. The main resort and recreational area of the Turkish state is the Black Sea coast. This region stands out among the resort areas of the world with a wealth of recreational resources. First of all, many vacationers are attracted here by the convenience of the climate for human health.

The country also has sandy beaches with healing properties in the Sea of Marmara (Bursa, the tourist center of Istanbul), the Aegean coast (the villages of Bodrum and Marmaris), the Mediterranean coast (Antalya, Alanya, Kemer, Side). recreation development.

Although the fact that the Czech Republic is one of the centers of ancient civilization contributed to the development of historical tourism, its favorable natural conditions indicate that it is very rich in recreational resources. Geographically, the country is located at an altitude of 1200-1400 m above sea level, and artificial lakes are used for recreation of the population. For example, in areas such as Lipno (4870 ha), Viltava (1558 ha), such opportunities have been created. Also, the presence in the country of many medicinal mineral waters, mineral and thermal springs, healing dirty lakes allow them to be widely used in recreation. The Russian part of the Black Sea coast also has rich recreational resources.

The main resort area located here is the Sochi climatic and recreational recreation area, which includes

the Adler, Khostiansky and Lazorensky districts. The peculiarity of the Sochi resort area is that the main methods of treatment in this sanatorium are climatotherapeutic balneological (with sulfur and iodine). The resort has 3 seasons instead of 4 a year, when hot and humid weather gives way to a long autumn. Late autumn gives way to early spring. The temperature will rise to +25°C in the Black Sea and +28°C in the Sea of Azov. Such favorable climatic conditions are favorable for human health [Maslov E.P., Crimea does not lose its charm even in the cold season, the average temperature does not exceed -10. This temperature rises to +15. The Crimean climate has healing properties, where millions of people come to improve their health. The arrival of tourists to the Crimean peninsula falls mainly on their own months. Many well-known "resort cities" of Crimea: Evpatoria, Saki, Yalta, Alupka, Alushta, Fedosia offer recreational services around the clock. The specific methods of treatment of these sanatoriums are gyration therapy (mud therapy). Such therapeutic muds are located in 5 places: Evpatoria, Tarkhanut, Kerch, Perekop and Chongaro-Arabat (Prisivash district), 3 of which have recreational properties. With this method, a number of diseases can be cured immediately. In the Sakisanatorium, patients are treated with this method, and it is known in the world as the "Saksimethod". However, in Crimea, brackish water is used only for tourism purposes. From the balneological method (mineral waters), the following 3 regions are located in the Crimean Plain, the Folded Region

(highlands) and the Kerch Peninsula. There are about 120 mineral waters springs on the peninsula, about 30 of which are used in medicine. The mineral composition of water includes nitrogen, sulfur, methane, carbon dioxide, hydrogen sulfide, bromine, iodine and other elements that help in the effective treatment of various diseases.

In addition, tourism and recreation play a key role in the economy of the neighboring Kyrgyz Republic. However, the flow of tourists is relatively small. This is because the infrastructure is not very well organized. There are 46 registered sanatoriums in Kyrgyzstan, and the government is taking steps to reconstruct them.

The territory of Kyrgyzstan has ample opportunities for the development of recreation and is characterized by relief and favorable natural conditions. The main resort areas of Issyk-Kul, Issyk-Ata, Ak-su, Chuponota, Tamga and others have a favorable relief at an altitude of 2000 m above sea level. In the hot gray resort area, radiation provides a circular motion, humidity of 65%, which can fluctuate between 7-8% throughout the year. Favorable climatic conditions are favorable for the organization of recreational services.

Currently, about 100 mineral waters have been identified in the Issyk-Kul region, and almost all types of mineral waters are found according to the classifications of Ivanova and Nivraeva. The most common types of these waters are silica, nitrogen and thermal waters. The world fame of the southern regions in the balneotherapy of sulfuric waters, radon waters, recreation of the Jeti-Oguz, Karabalta, Kokmerinsky regions is the high

content of radon in the water (1100 mcurie / l) [Nizamiyev A.G., There are many types of recreational resources in our country. However, they are mainly used by the local

population. With the development of recreational areas, it is advisable to assess the resource potential of the regions in this regard and take the necessary measures to attract foreign tourists.

References:

1. Маслов Е.П. Крым. Москва: «Географгиз», 1954г. Низамиев А.Г. Рекреационный комплекс Киргизистана: реалии и перспективы. Бишкек: «Илим», 1998г.
2. Солдатова А.С. Экономическая оценка рекреационных ресурсов как основа рационального природо-пользования // Культура народов Причерноморья. Но Симферополь, 2002. - С. 164-170.
3. М.М.Маҳмудов Ўзбекистонда туристик соҳасини бошқариш тизимининг ҳозирги ҳолат/ Ижтимоий соҳани модернизациялаш ва ривожлантиришнинг устувор йўналишлари мавзусидаги республика илмий-амалий конференцияси материаллар.- Тошкент, 2018.306-310 б.
4. Маҳмудов М.М. Жўраев Ш.С Ўзбекистонда туризм саноатининг ривожланишининг айрим масалари фан таълимни ривожлантиришда ёшларнинг ўрни Ўзбекистон республикаси фанлар академиясининг 75-йиллик юбилейига бағишланган Республика миқёсидаги илмий ва амалий конференция матреаллари-Тошкент,2018-йил. 227-229 б.
5. Маҳмудов М.М "Андижон вилоятида туризм ривожланишининг иқтисодий географик хусусиятлари" монографияси Тошкент 2021 йил. Мирзаев, Муротжон Аҳмаджонович. Туризм асослари: бакалавриат таълим йўналишлари талабалари учун ўқув қўлланма. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Олий ва ўрта махсус таълим вазирлиги. Т.: Ўзбекистон файласуфлари миллий жамияти нашриёти, 2011. - 12 б